

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: VAN HERWAARDE****FIRST NAME: ELIAS****PROGRAM CODE: DIPH****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references.

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID).

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 1%

The author used the following software: MSWord 2021 on Mac

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP):

1. The difference between UK and US English language (EUCLID 2021, 24-32)
2. Referencing Requirements (EUCLID 2021, 35-36)
3. The use of Latin abbreviations (EUCLID 2021, 58-64)
4. The use of a style guide (EUCLID 2021, 40-42)
5. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 33-34)
6. Zotero (Bradburn, n.d.)
7. Structure of essay (EUCLID 2021, 9-12)

INTERNATIONAL ACADEMIC WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

Embarking on doctoral education is something that I have considered for a long time, and I am excited to have finally decided to start this study journey. I am thrilled with the responsive and helpful faculty at EUCLID. However, I feel there is a lot to learn and understand, and there are some new topics I have not covered in several years. I have managed to log on to the Course Management System (CMS), start the course, log on to the Learning Management System (LSM), and understand how to navigate the system. I know that all of these small but new tasks, such as navigation of the LMS, will become easier over time, and therefore, my learning will become more accessible.

2) THE DIFFERENCE IN UK AND US ENGLISH LANGUAGE

I have lived in Australia, America, and the United Kingdom, where I was able to experience the differences within the English language. While reading this period's coursework, I was surprised that there were significantly more differences than I had expected, including spelling, pronunciation, and grammatical formation (EUCLID 2021, 27). I recognise that I need to ensure that I only use one style within my writing to ensure continuity and clarity.

3) REFERENCING REQUIREMENTS

While reading, I was interested in learning that references are not required for concepts considered common knowledge (EUCLID 2021, 37). This concept is new to me; however, it makes sense, and upon reflection, it is something that I agree with. In my previous study, I have always been advised that the more references, the better, and this will allow for the highest level of academic validity to a piece of work. Discussing specific common knowledge without referencing will allow for a more effortless flow of writing and will be easier for the reader to understand and follow. Upon further research, I was interested to see that other than common knowledge, other things do not need to be referenced such as historical events (Harvard University, n.d.).

4) THE USE OF LATIN ABBREVIATIONS

There are some rarely seen Latin abbreviations, and some are used in daily communication, such as A.M. and Per capita. I was very interested to read that Latin abbreviations should not be used in academic or official writing (EUCLID 2021, 59). I believe this to be controversial as I have read many academic papers that have used common Latin terms such as per capita or p.m. I agree that most Latin abbreviations are too obscure and would not be clearly understood by most readers in academic and official papers. This is something that I will need to be mindful of throughout my study, ensuring that I maintain continuity in my papers and do not use Latin abbreviations in my academic writing.

5) THE USE OF A STYLE GUIDE

Style guides must be used in academic writing to maintain continuity (University of Luxembourg, 2023). I have explored several different style guides and decided to use Chicago Rules with EUCLID for ease and continuity, as this is their recommended style guide. Other style guides that I reviewed included the Cambridge and World Health Organisation (WHO) guides. While undertaking the pre-reading for period one, I was very interested to read that as there are no universal rules of the English language, there is always

some debate over the style of writing (EUCLID 2021, 41). This is not a concept I have previously contemplated, reinforcing the need for a style guide.

6) PLAGIARISM

Plagiarism is a universally well-known topic in academia, and whilst reading through the coursework for period one, most concepts were not new to me. There was one part that I found interesting. The maximum similarity accepted at EUCLID through Grammarly is 18%. This is new to me as in previous academia, I have been told that no percentage is too high, and if you ensure that you reference where required, it would be acceptable to have similarity as high as 40-50%. I think this target of 18% is good and seems to be a fair number, allowing some scope for referencing but also encouraging new ideas and paraphrasing to be used more.

7) ZOTERO

The use of a reference management system is a new concept to me to be used for all papers. In my previous study, I used such systems on occasion but not regularly, and therefore, this is something that I expect may take some time to get used to. As with all new software, there are specifics that a user must learn to be proficient in its use. Using Zotero as a reference management system can increase accuracy with referencing and save time (Bradburn, n.d.). This system can seamlessly integrate with Google and Microsoft Word to easily collect, record, and input references in your writing.

8) STRUCTURE OF ESSAY

It was nice to refresh the structure of an academic paper and essay; whilst this was a topic that I was relatively confident with before starting this degree, there were some topics that I was happy to refresh. Ensuring that the thesis statement is close to the front of the essay is essential, and this has been reinforced by my further research suggesting that it is crucial to place the thesis statement for academic writing or the main topic of an essay as close to the start as possible as well as covering this again in the conclusion (Macdonald 2015; EUCLID 2021). Having a clear structure will also assist the reader in maintaining flow and engaging with the content and topic that is being discussed (University of Edinburgh, n.d.).

9) CONCLUSION

In conclusion, I have enjoyed reviewing this period, and I was able to refresh some information that I have not used in a long time. I also learned some new ideas about academic writing. I have thoroughly enjoyed this period and look forward to further study in this course. Some key takeaways from this period for my academic journey are to ensure

that I conform to a style guide, comprehensively understand Turabian referencing, and conform to EUCLID assessment requirements.

REFERENCES

Bradburn, Steven, dir. n.d. *How To Use Zotero (A Complete Beginner's Guide)*. YouTube. https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=JG7Uq_JFDzE&t=6s.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2021. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Bangui: Euclid University.

Harvard University. n.d. "The Exception: Common Knowledge." Harvard University. *The Exception: Common Knowledge* (blog).

Macdonald, Shem. 2015. *A Typical Structure for an Academic Essay*. Melbourne: Victoria University.

University of Edinburgh. n.d. *English Literature Writing Guide*. Edinburgh: University of Edinburgh.

University of Luxembourg. 2023. *Academic Writing: A Style Guide for Students*. Luxembourg: University of Luxembourg.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.